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Source:

1. Dunn, Michael John. *A Grammar of Chukchi*. dissertation, Australian National University, 1999. (from resources folder)

Phonetic inventory (for the Telqep variety of Chukchi) (p. 37)

-13 segmental consonant phonemes (see below for their possible realizations):

/p t k q m n ŋ ɬ s~c w r j ɣ/

-note: /r s c/ have different distributions depending on the gender of the speaker - see below

-note: Dunn transcribes the apico-alveolar affricate (IPA = ts) with c

-note: Dunn transcribes the velar approximant (IPA = ɰ) with ɣ

-note: Dunn frequently transcribes ɬ as simply l.

-2 prosodic phonemes:

-vowel harmony

-glottalization (sometimes considered the 14th consonant)

-3 vowel phonemes:

/i e u/

with the following 5 realizations:

[i e a o u]

-potentially, /ə/ could also be posited, while [ə] definitely exists due to schwa-epenthesis

(see discussion p. 40)

-no diphthongs (p. 42)

Basics for P-ω

-“instances in which the grammatical word does not correspond to the phonological word are limited” (p. 38)

-“The Chukchi phenomenon of vowel harmony provides a simple diagnostic for wordhood, as the phonological domain of the vowel harmony prosody is almost always coextensive with the grammatical unit ‘word’” (p. 61)

-for the few exceptions (in which a grammatical word consists of two or more words), see below!

The surface form of a word consists of any number of syllables of the following pattern (p.38-40):

CV(C) or *potentially* word-initially as V(C)

(in other words, unless a word has an initial V, the first C of a syllable is always filled)

-each syllable may or may not have glottalization prosody (see below)

-if the underlying form doesn't specify the necessary V (in other words, if it's form is C or CC), there's an epenthetic [ə]

/ŋe.wc.qet/ → [ŋe.wəc.qet] 'woman'

-however, if the underlying form is C₁C₂V... and C₂ is /c r ɬ/, then the ə-epenthesis is optional:

/mren/ → [mren] ~ [məren] 'mosquito'

(see p. 39-40 for diagrams of these abstract processes)

Deletion rule for underlying sequences of vowels in a word (p. 41):

/V₁V₂/ → [V₂] or /V/ → ø / _V

Deletion rule for underlying /ə/ in a word (p. 41):

when a prefix with final V is added to a stem with initial ə, this ə gets deleted.

(Dunn doesn't give any concrete examples)

Vowel-approximant assimilation for some limited homonym pairs (p. 42)

-word internal

-normally optional, but sometimes only the long-vowel version occurs

-this is no longer productive

$/V_1CV_2/ \rightarrow [V_1CV_2] \sim [V_2V_2] / C = /w \ r \ j \ \gamma/$ (ie: if C is an approximant)

ex:

$/qora/ \rightarrow [qora] \sim [qaa]$ 'reindeer'

$/\gamma iwik/ \rightarrow [\gamma iwik] \sim [\gamma iik]$ 'year'

The two prosodic phonemes:

1. vowel harmony (VH) "extends over the prosodic domain of the word" (p. 47)

-phonetic vowel segments:

[i e a o u] which are involved in VH

[ə] which only occurs epenthetically and does NOT participate in VH.

-Since VH is a prosodic phoneme, every word either exhibits it or it doesn't; so, each realized word has one of these characteristics: +VH or -VH.

-the underlying vowels /i e u/ are realized as follows (dependent on the characteristic \pm VH):

$/i//e//u/-VH[i][e][u]+VH[e][a][o]$ - "The prosodic domain of the vowel harmony prosody is the entire word. Thus, if the vowel harmony prosody is present in any one morpheme of a word then all vowels of the word are affected by it. The vowel harmony prosody itself is an independent phonological unit, and is not attached to any particular segment." (p. 48) - ie:

+VH > -VH

example (p. 48):

-absolute singular affixes

$/-n^{+VH}/$ 'nominalizer (derives place nouns from action verbs)'

$/-n^{-VH}/$ 'default absolute suffix'

thus the verb root $/tə\text{t}e^{-VH}/$ 'go, walk' becomes:

$[tə\text{t}a-n^{+VH}]$ 'path'

while the noun stem $/kem\text{t}i\text{t}u^{-VH}/$ 'kamlejka' (a cloth tunic) becomes:

$[kem\text{t}i\text{t}u-n^{-VH}]$ in the absolute case.

2. glottalization - this only operates in the domain of the syllable; for further info, see pp. 48-9.

Reduplication (p. 48-9, 105-110):

-is one of the possible markers for absolute singular

-copies consonants and vowels, but not glottal stops (which are due to glottalization)

-the VH affects the entire reduplicated form (as it always affects the entire P- ω in Chukchi)

example:

/weri-^{+VH}/ 'fork' → [wʔare-war] 'fork' (ABS-sg)

Vowel Reduction (VR) (p. 53, 106-7)

-word-final vowels are reduced or elided

-these processes are "almost obligatory" with word final lexical stems (zero derived nominals) but very uncommon with grammatical suffixes

-examples:

-reduction for /e^{-VH}/

/e^{-VH}/ → [ə] / _#

ex: /wala/ → [walə] 'knife' (ABS-sg)

-elision for /i^{-VH}, u^{-VH}, e^{-VH}/ (not as regular as the reduction rule)

/i^{-VH}, u^{-VH}, e^{-VH}/ → ∅ / _#

ex: /ewicu/ → [ewic] 'bag for plant gathering' (ABS-sg)

Stress (p. 53-4)

-not phonologically distinctive

-primary stress on first syllable of a word which has a consonant onset and a full vowel;
secondary stress is on every second syllable before and after the primary stress

examples:

first σ = C+fullV

[ʔ ʔ nu.tec.qə.cə.ku.kin] 'something from the surface of the ground'

first σ = reduced V(s)

[qə. ʔ ʔ jet.ɾ ʔ i] 'come!'

[kəɾ.ɾ ə. ʔ ʔ re.cʔə.kin] 'something made of dry stumps'

first σ = V-initial

[a. ʔ ʔ tok.tor.kə] 'without a doctor'

[a. ʔ ʔ mo.ʔe.qaj] 'bark' (DIM)

Vocative Prosody (p. 54-5)

-applies to the final syllable of a word

-prosodic change(s) to words when they are being called out or very strongly emphasized

-not a morpheme

-applied indiscriminately to words of any class in any grammatical form

-not all possible prosodic changes are necessarily applied

-the changes are:

-epenthetic [ə] in final σ → [o]

-non-epenthetic [ə] (due to vowel reduction) in final σ → full vowel

-lengthening of V in final σ

-word-final V → V+j

-to add even more emphasis, the following changes are also possible:

- laryngeal constriction
- lengthening of non-final V(s) of a word
 - applied either to all Vs or only full Vs

examples:

/təʔəʔən/ → [təʔəʔo::n] 'Təʔəʔən!' (a name)

/req-ə-ʔet-ə-rkən/ → [req-ə-ʔet-ə-rko::n] 'what the hell are you doing?'

(*rkən* is a progressive verb suffix)

for more examples, see p. 55

Chukchi's clitic: the emphatic discourse particle (clitic) /ɤʔm/ (p. 76)

-very common

-joins phonologically to words of any word class (thus a clitic)

-phonological rules:

-if the host has a final vowel, this vowel is glottalized by /ɤʔm/:

/cewaro=ʔm/ → [cewarʔom] 'gray reindeer (EMPH)'

-if the host has a final consonant, a syllable is formed for /ɤʔm/ with an epenthetic

schwa:

/remkəʔən=ʔm/ → [remkəʔənʔəm] 'guest (EMPH)'

Three cases for non-alignment of P- ω and G- ω :

1. postpositions

-one version of the word-internal velar stop assimilation (/k/ → [ɣ] / $_C$ -back) can also intermittently be triggered by either of Chukchi's two postpositions /qaca/ 'near' and /reen/ 'together with'; these could thus be considered enclitics (p. 77).

-However, they do not interact with VH (which is generally a test for P- ω hood).

example:

/əʔʔa-k reen/ → [əʔʔa-ɣ reen]

mother.LOC with.PP 'with mother'

-additionally, in spontaneous texts /reen/ does not always have its locative case nominal adjacent to it [it would be interesting to know if it still triggers velar stop assimilation in this case, but Dunn doesn't go into this].

2. analytic numerals

-"...when an analytic numeral functions as a nonabsolute argument there are instances of morphological marking which apply over the entire analytic numeral as if it were a single word. A good example is circumfixation; when phonological and grammatical words are coextensive no question arises, but when the grammatical word is an analytic numeral consisting of several phonological words the circumfix is resolved into a prefix for the first word and a suffix for the last word. Such structures are not attested in the spontaneous data used for this description, as Russian numerals have taken over all but the simple numerals." (p. 68)

-no examples given for an analytic number with circumfixation, but here's at least an analytic number (p. 303):

kətʔən-qʔek-ken qʔik-kin amŋəroot-ken paroʔ
fifteen-twenty-NUM twenty-NUM eight-NUM extra

'three hundred and twenty eight'

...and two examples of case-marking circumfixes for nominals (the last element of an analytic number *paroʔ* is a noun - p. 302):

-comitative (with) (p. 116): γe -___-te^{-VH} ~ γe -___-e^{-VH} (first variant for V-final stems)

-privative (without) (p. 117): e-___-ke
 so I presume that the following (my example) could possibly maybe perhaps by chance be an example of one grammatical word consisting of several phonological words:
 e<-kətʰən-qʰek-ken qʰik-kin amŋəroot-ken parɔʰ->ke
 without<-15-20-NUM 20-NUM 8-NUM extra->
 'without three hundred and twenty eight'

3. analytic verbs

- verbs consisting of two phonological words formed from an auxiliary and an uninflecting lexical head (usually comprised of a verb base, an adverbial form derived from the verb or adjective classes).

example (analytic verb is underlined):

winwə-t qonpə ʰəɾi n-ine-ʰɾ-ə-qin
 track-3plABS always know.Vbase HAB-TR-AUX-E-3s
 'he always knows their scent'

Phonological processes which cause phonological alternations at morpheme boundaries (and not at word boundaries):

-anterior stops assimilate nasality with a following nasal:

/p/ → [m] / C₊nasal

/t/ → [n] / C₊nasal

-velar stop /k/ has an approximant allophone before C (lenition) and assimilates in place with following uvular:

/k/ → [ɾ] / C₋back

/k/ → [q] / q

-glottalization prosody for underlying uvular stop /q/ before C (except /q/):

/q/ → [ʔ] / C (where C≠q)

-the consonant /s/ is only used by men and has two possibilities in free variation:

/s/ → [s]~[tʃ]

-the consonant /c/ (note: in IPA this is /ts/) is only used by women and is subject to the following rules:

/c/ → [t] / #

/c/ → [s] / q

-the lateral fricative /ɬ/:

/ɬ/ → [ɬ]~[tʃ] / ɬ

-the nasals:

/m/ → [m]

/n/ → [n]

but /ŋ/ is subject to the following rules:

/ŋ/ → [ɾ] / C₊nasal +anterior

/ŋ/ → [n] / ɾ₋

/ŋ/ → α place / C₋nasal α place (note: [α place] limited to possible nasals, ie:

bilabial, alveolar, or velar)

-the approximants:

/w/ → [w]

/ɾ/ → [ɾ] (note: in IPA this is [ɰ])

and the following approximants with rules:

/r/ → [ɾ] / C₊coronal

/j/ / ɹ / ɻ / ɰ / ɰ_ +coronal

-the semi-vowel approximants trigger assimilation of place for a neighboring schwa:

/ə/ → [i] / _j or j_

/ə/ → [u] / _w or w_

-the non-coronal approximants /w ɹ / undergo the non-coronal cluster transformation when neighboring another non-coronal C:

C₁-coronal -nasal α sonorant C₂-coronal -nasal β sonorant → [kw] / at least α or β is +

(in words: any cluster of two non-nasal, non-coronal Cs in which at least one C is a sonorant is realized as [kw])

(this is sometimes avoided in careful speech and avoided for /q/)

FYI:

-correspondences between phonological systems of the gender dialects (p. 47):

men men's

phoneme women's phoneme

women translation

[qoraŋə]/r//r/[qoraŋə]reindeer[panrat]/r//c/[pancat]leg hide[sajok]/s//c/[cajok]to drink tea-

these correspondences are explicable diachronically, but unpredictable synchronically